

MECHANICAL IN PLANE PERFORMANCE OF AEROTISS[®] 4/5D

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SUMMARY: Aerotiss[®] 4/5D is a technique to produce thick, multi-layered preforms, reinforced through the thickness by stitching. The stitching guarantees the stability of the preform during processing. Moreover, it gives the final composite an excellent delamination resistance and fracture toughness. RTM was used to impregnate the preforms with an epoxy resin system. The influence of the stitching on the mechanical in plane performance was studied for quasi-isotropic glass and carbon preforms. Smaller stitch spacing causes a slight decrease in stiffness and a certain decrease in strength. This is more pronounced for the carbon preforms. The stitches act as stress concentrators during loading. Computer tomography revealed that the fibres in the 0°/90° layers remain straight, but that in the +/-45° layers, the stitching causes undulation. A geometric model is being developed to refine the laminate plate model for these Aerotiss[®] 4/5D composites.

KEYWORDS: Aerotiss[®] 4/5D, mechanical in plane performance, stitching, quasi-isotropic preforms, laminate plate model, computer tomography, glass-epoxy, carbon-epoxy

INTRODUCTION

Aerotiss[®] 4/5D is a technique developed by Aerospatiale to produce thick, multi-layered preforms, reinforced through the thickness by stitching. Aerotiss[®] 4/5D is well suited to produce highly loaded structural parts with RTM. The stitching guarantees the stability of the preform during processing and provides an increased delamination resistance in the final composite. In this paper, the in plane mechanical performance is evaluated for different variations of Aerotiss[®] 4/5D. The improvement of the fracture toughness by the stitching will be discussed at the 2nd ESIS TC4 Conference on Polymers and Composites, 13-15 September Switzerland.

Manufacturing process for Aerotiss[®] 4/5D

First, a robot lays down the fibres on a plate with a pin frame for fixation (see Fig. 1). Layers of 0° , 90° , $\pm 45^\circ$ can be stacked in an arbitrary sequence. It is also possible to incorporate other layers in the stacking like mats to improve the surface quality, or like foam layers to realise a sandwich structure.

Fig. 1: Fibre placement for Aerotiss[®] 4/5D

Next, the layers are stitched together through the thickness. Fig. 2 shows simple stitching: the stitching loops formed at the bottom are free. Using chain stitching results in interconnected stitching loops.

Fig. 2: Stitching for Aerotiss[®] 4/5D

Choosing the stitch spacing equal to the pin spacing of the frame realises maximal preform stability, because all in plane yarns are bonded by stitch yarns and minimal fibre damage, because the needle passes through a hole (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Holes in $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ layers where needle will go through

The radius of these holes equals:

$$\min_b \left(\frac{d - b_{0^\circ/90^\circ}}{2}, \frac{d/\sqrt{2} - b_{+/-45^\circ}}{2} \right)$$

with: b = width of the fibre
d = stitch spacing

Aerotiss[®] 4/5D remains stable after cutting (scissor blade cutter or waterjet). Complex preforms can be made by assembling several Aerotiss[®] 4/5D parts with stitching. In the Brite Euram project Multexcomp, this technique is being demonstrated for a helicopter gearbox.

Composite processing of Aerotiss[®] 4/5D

The Aerotiss[®] 4/5D preforms were impregnated with an epoxy resin system (Araldite LY 564 – Hardener HY 2954 by Ciba Geigy) by means of vacuum assisted, pressure controlled RTM. The resin was preheated at 60°C and degassed. Injection is performed and the plate is cured for 1 hour at 80°C in the mould. The transparent top mould (PMMA) allows to visually check the injection, but it limits the maximum mould temperature to 80°C. Hence post-curing in an oven is necessary (1 hour at 140°C). The PMMA top mould also limits the clamping pressure, so that the fibre volume fractions of 45% up to 55% are obtained. The glass-epoxy specimens are completely transparent, quality control can be done visually. C-scanning is used to inspect the carbon-epoxy specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Material variations and Test description

An overview of the tested material variations is given in Table 1 and Table 2.

Aerotiss [®] 4/5 D – glass variations				
Plane filling	<i>Filling yarn</i>	RO 99 320		
	<i>Lay-up</i>	(0-45-90-135)*4/s = 32 layers : quasi-isotropic		
Stitching	<i>Stitching type</i>	<i>Stitch spacing</i>	<i>Nr.stitch yarns</i>	<i>Type of stitch yarn</i>
	4x4/1	4mmx4 mm	1	glass 272 tex
	2.5x2.5/1	2.5mmx2.5mm	1	glass 272 tex
	4x4/2	4mmx4 mm	2	R0 99 320

Table 1: Glass variations

Aerotiss [®] 4/5 D – carbon variations				
Plane filling	<i>Filling yarn</i>	tenax HTA 5331 200 tex		
	<i>Lay-up</i>	(0-45-90-135)*3/s = 24 layers : quasi-isotropic		
Stitching	<i>Stitching type</i>	<i>Stitch spacing</i>	<i>Nr.stitch yarns</i>	<i>Type of stitch yarn</i>
	4x4/1	4mmx4 mm	1	tenax HTA 5331 200 tex
	2.5x2.5/1	2.5mmx2.5mm	1	tenax HTA 5331 200 tex
	4x4/2	4mmx4 mm	2	tenax HTA 5331 200 tex

Table 2: Carbon variations

Tensile testing was performed on specimen of 230mmx25mm in the direction: 0°, 30° or 22.5°, 90° (parallel to stitch = 0°). The testing speed was 2 mm/min for the glass-epoxy specimen and 1 mm/min for the carbon-epoxy specimen. The load and both the longitudinal and transverse strain were monitored. The in plane elastic (E_{11} , ν_{12} , G_{12}) and strength properties were determined.

Experimental results compared with theoretical predictions

The experimental values are summarised in Table 3 and Table 4, which also include theoretical values. By using the ratio of the experimental vs. these theoretical values (mentioned as exp/theor in Table 3 and Table 4), the differences in fibre volume fraction (Vf) can be neglected and an overall comparison can be made.

The theoretical values were calculated based on the laminate plate theory, using the formulas of Chamis [1] for the ply properties. So, the theoretical values refer to a non-stitched laminate with perfectly straight fibres. The theoretical values provide an upper limit : due to the stitching, the fibres do not remain perfectly straight. Moreover, the simplified stress assumptions of the laminate plate theory will further cause a small overestimation. Another limitation of the laminate plate theory is the assumption of infinite plate dimensions which causes the theoretical off axis strength in Table 4 to be too high.

Carbon-epoxy		E_{qi} (GPa)			nu			G (GPa)		
stitch type	Vf (%)	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor
4x4/1	48,5	35,5	43,5	82%	0,34	0,32	106%	13,2	16,5	80%
2.5x2.5/1	51	35	45	78%	0,33	0,32	103%	13,2	17	78%
4x4/2	50	35,5	44,5	80%	0,34	0,32	106%	13,2	16,9	78%

Glass-epoxy		E_{qi} (GPa)			nu			G (GPa)		
stitch type	Vf (%)	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor
4x4/1	54,5	21,5	22,7	95%	0,33	0,30	110%	8,1	7,4	109%
2.5x2.5/1	46,5	17,7	19,4	91%	0,33	0,30	110%	6,7	7,3	92%
4x4/2	53,5	20,5	22,27	92%	0,32	0,30	107%	7,8	6,3	123%

Table 3: Experimental results – tensile elastic properties

with : E_{qi} = quasi-isotropic E-modulus

nu = Poisson modulus

G = shear modulus

Carbon-epoxy		$\sigma_{ultimate}^{0^\circ}$			$\sigma_{ultimate}^{22.5^\circ}$			$\sigma_{ultimate}^{90^\circ}$		
stitch type	Vf (%)	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor
4x4/1	48,5	480	585	82%	390	705	55%	472	585	81%
2.5x2.5/1	51	420	605	69%	380	730	52%	488	605	81%
4x4/2	50	460	600	77%	390	720	54%	456	600	76%

Glass-epoxy		$\sigma_{ultimate}^{0^\circ}$			$\sigma_{ultimate}^{30^\circ}$		
stitch type	Vf (%)	exp	theor	exp/theor	exp	theor	exp/theor
4x4/1	54,5	360	370	97%	275	420	65%
2.5x2.5/1	46,5	280	325	86%	265	360	74%
4x4/2	53,5	335	360	93%	300	413	73%

Table 4: Experimental results – tensile strength properties

Conclusions :

The quasi-isotropic laminates have an isotropic stiffness, but an anisotropic strength behaviour. Comparing the exp/theor values reveals that for both stiffness and strength, the stitch variations can be classified from high to low as 4x4/1, 4x4/2, 2.5x2.5/1. So, the stitch spacing has a bigger influence than the number of used stitch threads.

	Stiffness		Strength	
	<i>carbon-epoxy</i>	<i>glass-epoxy</i>	<i>carbon-epoxy</i>	<i>glass-epoxy</i>
4x4/1	reference	reference	reference	reference
4x4/2	-2.2 %	-2.6 %	-6.6 %	-4.4 %
2.5x2.5/1	-4.7 %	-3.7 %	-15.4 %	-11.5 %

Table 5: Overview of the property variations (decrease in % taking 4x4/1 as a reference)

Table 5 shows that the variation in stiffness is limited and close from the experimental resolution. The variation in strength is however considerable. Especially for carbon-epoxy, a less dense stitching is favourable for the strength.

Material behaviour up to failure

Glass-epoxy

As mentioned before, the glass-epoxy specimens are transparent. This allows visual monitoring of the damage development during loading. At about 20 % of the maximum load, small cracks start to appear around all the stitches, accompanied by a clicking noise, leaving the stitches as opaque points. The stitches act as stress concentrators. Then, the zones between the stitches become gradually less transparent and lines (debonded fibres) become visible, first in the layers with an orientation close to 90°. The surface of the specimens remains intact at this point. A more intensive cracking announces final failure, which happens in an explosive like way, with a lot of fibre debonding.

Fig. 4: Damage development in 2.5x2.5/1 glass-epoxy specimen in 30° off-axis tensile test

Carbon-epoxy

A similar clicking noise is observed from about 20 % of the maximum load on. However, externally no damage can be seen. Final failure is sudden; the damaged zone around the crack is more limited compared to glass.

CHARACTERISATION

Optical microscopy was used to study the layer thickness. At the bottom of the preform, the loops of the stitches form a knit like layer with a higher resin content.

The fibre geometry in the different layers was studied using computer tomography. For glass-epoxy, the contrast between fibre and matrix was good, however for carbon-epoxy the contrast was poor. The contrast is mainly affected by the differences in density and in atomic number. The difference in atomic number is smaller for carbon fibre versus epoxy matrix compared to glass fibre versus epoxy.

Fig. 5: CT-scan of 90° layer and -45° layer for a glass epoxy specimen

The CT-scan of a 90° and -45° layer in Fig. 5 reveals that the fibres in the 0°/90° layers remain straight, but that in the +/-45° layers get a zig-zag pattern. A refined laminate plate model is being developed taking into account this zig-zag geometry (see Fig. 6) to improve the theoretical values in Table 3 and Table 4.

Fig. 6: Geometric model for a 0° and -45° layer

In [2], Prodromou discusses another modelling approach for Aerotiss[®] 4/5D. The yarn geometry of the dry preform is studied with a stereo microscope and described in detail: the yarn crimp, the yarn path and the yarn shape. Together with the fibre-matrix properties, this is used as input for the FLEXCOMP program. FLEXCOMP is an implementation of a poly-inclusion model solved using a self-consistent or a Mori-Tanaka mean field schemes (see [3]). With this approach, Prodromou finds better approximations for the theoretical values, especially for the carbon Aerotiss[®] 4/5D.

CONCLUSIONS

Aerotiss[®] 4/5D is very versatile technology: thick preforms (up to 30 mm and more) can be realised with an arbitrary ply stacking sequence and with different types of fibres (glass, carbon, aramid, ...). The stitching gives the preform a high stability and enhances the delamination resistance tremendously in the final composite. Compared to non z-reinforced preforms, there is a small decrease in in plane performance, but this can be minimised by a good choice of the stitching parameters: a bigger stitch spacing is preferable.

By monitoring the transparent glass-epoxy specimen during loading, it was shown that the stitches act as stress concentrators that initiate damage homogeneously over the specimen. Computer tomography was used to study the fibre architecture. This information is being used to set-up a geometric model, that will be the basis for a refined laminate plate model for Aerotiss[®] 4/5D composites.

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